

Mixture-of-Experts under Finite-Rate Gating: Communication–Generalization Trade-offs

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Abstract—Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) architectures decompose prediction tasks into specialized expert sub-networks selected by a gating mechanism. This letter adopts a communication-theoretic view of MoE gating, modeling the gate as a stochastic channel operating under a finite information rate. Within an information-theoretic learning framework, we derive a mutual-information generalization bound and a rate-distortion characterization $D(R_g)$ of finite-rate gating, where $R_g := I(X; G_W(X))$, yielding $\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m + \sqrt{(2/m) I(S; W)}$. The analysis yields capacity-aware limits for communication-constrained MoE systems, and numerical simulations on synthetic multi-expert models empirically confirm the predicted trade-offs between gating rate, expressivity, and generalization.

Index Terms—Mixture of Experts, Generalization Bounds, Communication Trade-off, Rate-Distortion

I. INTRODUCTION

Mixture-of-Experts models [1], [2] combine multiple expert predictors through a gating network that assigns probabilistic weights or discrete routing decisions to experts. This modular structure enables specialization, scalability, and sparse activation in large neural architectures such as the Switch Transformer [3], where only a small subset of experts is active per input. Despite their practical success, the theoretical understanding of MoE systems—particularly their generalization behavior under finite communication resources—remains limited. Classical analyses [4] provided Rademacher-based bounds that depend additively on the complexity of the gating function and the sum of expert complexities, leading to bounds that scale linearly with the number of experts. More recently, Akretche *et al.* [5] introduced local differential privacy (LDP) regularization on the gating mechanism, obtaining tighter PAC-Bayesian and Rademacher risk bounds with logarithmic dependence on the number of experts. However, even in this privacy-regularized setting, the gating network is treated purely as a stochastic selector rather than as an information-constrained communication process.

The proposed communication-generalization framework for MoE, beyond its theoretical significance in distributed learning, finds a natural interpretation in aeronautical and aerospace communication systems [6], [7]. Modern aircraft, satellites, and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) increasingly rely on distributed sensing and computation architectures, where multiple onboard or remote modules act as *experts* processing heterogeneous streams of sensor data under stringent bandwidth, latency, and reliability constraints [8]. The gating mechanism of

an MoE parallels the routing logic in such systems—deciding which local estimator or control unit should communicate its information to the flight computer or ground segment. In this context, the mutual-information-based rate constraints derived here provide a principled measure of how much performance degradation (in estimation, navigation, or control) results from limited communication capacity, effectively extending *data-rate theorems* [9], [10] to the regime of learned, data-driven aerospace decision systems.

Novelty and Contribution: From a communication-theoretic perspective, this work develops an explicit *communication-generalization trade-off* for MoE models by reinterpreting the gating mechanism as a finite-capacity stochastic channel. We quantify the gating pathway by its mutual information rate $R_g = I(X; G_W(X))$, which limits how much information about the input can reach the expert bank and thus controls expressivity and statistical robustness. Building on this view, we introduce a rate-distortion formulation of the gating problem and show how the best achievable prediction risk at a given gating rate is characterized by a rate-distortion function $D(R_g)$, leading to the bound $\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m + \sqrt{(2/m) I(S; W)}$, where R_g enters through $D(R_g)$. We further consider the practically relevant case where gate decisions are conveyed over a physical link of capacity C ; when the gate is trained/regularized to operate near this budget (so that $I(X; G_W(X)) \approx C$), the bound specializes to $D(C)$, making the dependence on C explicit, and connects MoE gating to classical notions such as channel capacity and data-rate limitations.

While information-theoretic generalization theory [11], [12], communication-limited learning [13]–[15], and recent MoE risk bounds [5] are well established, to the best of our knowledge, they do not treat the MoE gate as a rate-limited channel nor provide risk bounds in which its communication rate explicitly appears as a design parameter. Related information-theoretic perspectives on specialization and hierarchical decision systems have also been studied, e.g., via mutual-information principles and online learning in hierarchical architectures [16]–[18]. Our contribution is to place MoE architectures within a unified rate-distortion and capacity framework, where the gating rate $I(X; G_W(X))$ acts as a system-level communication constraint (which, in practice, is upper-bounded by the available link capacity) shaping both expressivity and generalization, and where privacy or compression mechanisms can be interpreted as additional noisy-channel layers. Theoretical results are supported by numerical simulations on multi-expert MoE models and on a binary symmetric *one-bit gating* scenario, which empirically illustrate

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the predicted trade-offs between gating rate, sample size, and generalization performance.

Organization: Section II formalizes MoE models as stochastic communication systems. Section III applies information-theoretic generalization bounds to MoE gating. Section IV introduces a rate-distortion formulation of the gating mechanism and establishes a rate-distortion model combined with an information-theoretic generalization term. Section V presents numerical simulations that empirically validate the theoretical trade-offs, and Section VI concludes with perspectives for communication-aware MoE design.

II. MOE AS A COMMUNICATION SYSTEM

Let $(X, Y) \sim D$ with $X \in \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ and $Y \in \mathcal{Y}$. We consider a bank of n experts indexed by $[n] \triangleq \{1, \dots, n\}$. A (possibly stochastic) gating module parameterized by W_G defines a conditional distribution

$$P_{W_G}(G = g | X = x) = g_{W,g}(x), \quad g \in [n], \quad (1)$$

where $g_W(x) \triangleq (g_{W,1}(x), \dots, g_{W,n}(x)) \in \Delta_n$ is a probability simplex vector and $g_{W,g}(x)$ denotes its g -th component. Given G , the selected expert produces the prediction, i.e., $\hat{Y} = h_{G,W_H}(X)$. Unless stated otherwise, the gating operation is applied *per-sample* and is memoryless across samples conditioned on (X, W) . Let $S = \{(x_j, y_j)\}_{j=1}^m \sim D^m$ denote the training sample, and let $W = (W_G, W_H)$ denote the (possibly randomized) parameters produced by a learning algorithm trained on S^1 . For a bounded loss $\ell \in [0, 1]$, the population and empirical risks are defined as

$$R(W) = \mathbb{E}_{(X,Y) \sim D} \mathbb{E}_{G_W(X)} [\ell(h_{G_W(X),W}(X), Y)], \quad (2)$$

$$R_S(W) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbb{E}_{G_W(x_j)} [\ell(h_{G_W(x_j),W}(x_j), y_j)]. \quad (3)$$

The random gating decision $G_W(X)$ thus defines a discrete communication channel from inputs to experts, with *gating rate* $I(X; G_W(X))$, through which information about X flows into the prediction, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

III. INFORMATION-THEORETIC BOUND AND PROOF

We adopt the framework of information-theoretic learning theory [11], [12]. Let $I(S; W)$ denote the mutual information between the training sample and the learned parameters. This quantity measures how much the learned model depends on the data and therefore controls its expected generalization gap.

Theorem 1 (Generalization of MoE via Mutual Information). *Assume $\ell \in [0, 1]$. Let W be the (possibly randomized) parameters produced by a learning algorithm trained on sample $S = \{(x_j, y_j)\}_{j=1}^m \sim D^m$. Then, for any sample size $m \geq 1$, the expected generalization gap satisfies*

$$|\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)}, \quad (4)$$

¹For brevity we write $g_W(x)$ and $G_W(x)$ to mean the gate induced by W_G (with $W = (W_G, W_H)$).

Fig. 1: Mixture-of-Experts system viewed as a finite-rate stochastic communication link. The input feature vector X is first processed by the gating module, which implements a channel $P(G | X; W_G)$ that encodes X into a discrete routing index $G_W(X) \in [n]$ under an information-rate constraint. This index selects one of the distributed experts $\{h_{g,W}\}_{g=1}^n$, and the selected expert's output is used to form the final prediction \hat{Y} . In this representation, $I(X; G_W(X))$ quantifies the effective communication rate between the input and the expert bank, so that the gate behaves as a constrained link whose finite information budget limits how much information about X can reach the experts and thereby controls the overall expressivity and generalization performance of the MoE.

where $I(S; W)$ in (4) is the mutual information between the training sample and the learned parameters².

Proof. Let $(X, Y) \sim D$ denote a fresh, independent test example not contained in the training sample S . For a fixed set of learned parameters $W = (W_G, W_H)$, the MoE prediction for input X is obtained by sampling an expert index $T \sim g_W(X)$ from the gating distribution, and then evaluating the corresponding expert $h_{T,W}(X)$. Define the random variable

$$L = \ell(h_{T,W}(X), Y), \quad (5)$$

which represents the instantaneous test loss of the learned model. The randomness in L arises from two sources that are independent conditioned on W ; (i) the test point (X, Y) drawn from D , and (ii) the stochastic gating selection T conditioned on X and W . The population risk $R(W)$ and empirical risk $R_S(W)$ can be expressed as expectations of L :

$$R(W) = \mathbb{E}_{(X,Y) \sim D} \mathbb{E}_{T \sim g_W(X)} [L], \quad (6)$$

$$R_S(W) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbb{E}_{T \sim g_W(x_j)} [\ell(h_{T,W}(x_j), y_j)]. \quad (7)$$

Hence, the generalization gap, i.e., $\text{gen}(W) := \mathbb{E}[R(W) - R_S(W)]$, measures the deviation between test and training losses in expectation over all draws of S and W . In

²Unless stated otherwise, all mutual information and entropy quantities are measured in nats, i.e., logarithms are natural (ln). References to *bits* are purely informal; using base-2 logarithms would simply rescale these quantities by a factor of $\ln 2$.

information-theoretic learning theory [11], [12], the mutual information $I(S; W)$ quantifies how strongly the output of the learning algorithm depends on its input dataset. When $I(S; W)$ is small, the algorithm's output is nearly independent of any particular training sample, implying strong stability and small generalization error. Conditioned on W , both the test example (X, Y) and the gating randomization T are independent of S . That is, once the model parameters are fixed, the test loss L cannot reveal more information about S than W itself. Formally, this yields the Markov chain $S \rightarrow W \rightarrow L$, which by the data-processing inequality implies

$$I(S; L) \leq I(S; W) . \quad (8)$$

For any randomized learning algorithm producing parameters W from the sample S , and for any bounded loss $\ell \in [0, 1]$, the decoupling inequality stated in work of Xu and Raginsky [11, Lemma 1], combined with [11, Theorem 1], establishes that

$$|\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; L)} . \quad (9)$$

Substituting (8) into (9) gives

$$|\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} . \quad (10)$$

This is precisely the bound in (4). In the MoE context, the gating mechanism $g_W(X)$ introduces an additional layer of randomness beyond that in the learned parameters W . However, since this gating randomness is internal to the model and conditionally independent of the sample S once W is fixed, the same inequality holds. The resulting bound therefore quantifies how much the model's dependence on the data—captured by $I(S; W)$ —governs the generalization gap, regardless of the number of experts or the structure of the gating mechanism. This completes the proof. \square

Remark 1 (Communication interpretation). *The bound in Theorem 1 quantifies the estimation or learning-algorithm component of generalization through $I(S; W)$. Separately, the gating mechanism defines a communication channel $X \rightarrow G_W(X)$ with rate $I(X; G_W(X))$. Constraining this rate—e.g., via local differential privacy (LDP), where each input is first randomized by a local privacy mechanism, or via a rate-distortion objective—limits how much information the gate can transmit from the input to the experts, thereby controlling the model capacity. Thus, generalization is governed by $I(S; W)$, while expressivity and communication dependence are governed by $I(X; G_W(X))$. The novelty of our framework is that, although the mutual-information bound itself follows classical results, interpreting the gating mechanism as a finite-rate communication channel and explicitly linking its communication rate $I(X; G_W(X))$ to model expressivity and generalization has not appeared in prior analyses of MoE.*

IV. RATE-DISTORTION FORMULATION OF GATING

The gating mechanism can also be interpreted through a *rate-distortion* lens. It must encode each input X into a discrete message G of limited communication rate that still yields low prediction loss.

A. Rate-Distortion Optimization

The gating design problem can be posed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{P(G|X)} \quad & \mathbb{E}[\ell(h_G(X), Y)] , \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & I(X; G) \leq R_g , \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where the expectation is over an independent $(X, Y) \sim D$ and $G|X \sim P(\cdot|X)$. The above expresses the fundamental trade-off between communication rate and predictive performance. Equivalently, by introducing a Lagrange multiplier $\lambda > 0$, we can minimize

$$\mathcal{L}(P(G|X)) = \mathbb{E}[\ell(h_G(X), Y)] + \lambda I(X; G) . \quad (12)$$

The constrained problem (11) and its Lagrangian form (12) can be solved by classical rate–distortion iterations (e.g., Blahut-Arimoto) in settings where the distributions are tractable [19].

B. Rate-Distortion Function and Generalization Bound

We define the rate-distortion function as follows:

$$D(R_g) = \inf_{I(X; G) \leq R_g} \mathbb{E}[\ell(h_G(X), Y)] . \quad (13)$$

As a standard rate-distortion function, $D(R)$ is non-increasing in R . Throughout, we interpret $D(R_g)$ as $D_{W_H}(R_g)$, i.e., the rate-distortion function induced by the realized expert bank W_H (conditioned on W_H). In (13), the experts $\{h_g\}_g$ (equivalently, the expert parameters W_H) are kept fixed³; the infimum is taken over all conditional distributions $P(G|X)$ whose mutual information with X does not exceed R_g . Note that $D(R_g)$ represents the best achievable prediction loss under a communication rate constraint R_g . The following theorem combines rate-distortion and generalization principles.

Theorem 2 (Rate-Distortion-Generalization Bound). *Let $W = (W_G, W_H)$ denote the parameters produced by a learning algorithm trained on a sample $S \sim D^m$, and let $G_W(X)$ denote the corresponding (possibly stochastic) gating output. Define the effective gating rate as $R_g := I(X; G_W(X))$. Assume moreover that the expected empirical risk satisfies*

$$\mathbb{E}[R_S(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m , \quad (14)$$

for some nonnegative error term $\delta_m \geq 0$ (capturing optimization and empirical-to-population mismatch for the rate-distortion objective at rate R_g). Such a condition is satisfied, for example, when the gating parameters W_G are obtained (for the realized expert bank W_H) by approximately minimizing the empirical rate-distortion Lagrangian

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}}_S(W_G; W_H) \triangleq R_S(W_G, W_H) + \lambda I(X; G_W(X)) , \quad (15)$$

for some $\lambda > 0$, or equivalently by solving the constrained empirical problem in (11). In this case, δ_m captures the optimization sub-optimality and the empirical-to-population

³Equivalently, one may write $D(R_g) \equiv D_{W_H}(R_g)$ to emphasize that the rate-distortion function is induced by the fixed expert bank (conditioned on W_H).

mismatch of the rate-distortion objective at rate R_g . Then the expected population risk of the learned MoE satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m + \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} . \quad (16)$$

Proof. To obtain an upper bound on the expected population risk, write

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] = \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)] + (\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]) , \quad (17)$$

$$\leq \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)] + |\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| . \quad (18)$$

By the assumed approximate optimality of the learned gating mechanism, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[R_S(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m , \quad (19)$$

and from (19), we infer that

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m + |\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| . \quad (20)$$

Let $(X, Y) \sim D$ be an independent test point, and let $G_W(X) \in [n]$ denote the (possibly stochastic) gate output (expert index) induced by the learned parameters W (i.e., $G_W(X) \sim g_W(X)$ given X and W). Define the instantaneous test loss

$$L \triangleq \ell(h_{G_W(X), W}(X), Y) \in [0, 1] .$$

Next, we apply the same information-theoretic generalization bound used in the proof of Theorem 1 (cf. (9)), specialized to the instantaneous loss L , which yields

$$|\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; L)} . \quad (21)$$

In the MoE setting, the prediction loss involves the composition of two random mechanisms: (i) the learned parameters W , and (ii) the stochastic gating variable $G_W(X)$. However, conditioned on W , the gating variable $G_W(X)$ depends only on X and is independent of S , which implies the Markov chain $S \rightarrow W \rightarrow (X, Y, G_W(X), L)$, and hence

$$I(S; L) \leq I(S; W) . \quad (22)$$

Substituting into (21) yields

$$|\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - \mathbb{E}[R_S(W)]| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} . \quad (23)$$

Combining (20) with the above inequality yields

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m + \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} ,$$

which is the claimed bound on the expected population risk. \square

Remark 2 (Generalization trade-off in MoE under local privacy). *Theorem 1 provides an explicit communication-generalization frontier for MoE systems. Suppose that the gating mechanism is designed through an ϵ -LDP channel, meaning that each input X is passed through a randomized mechanism $Q(\cdot|X)$ that satisfies the standard per-sample privacy condition*

$$Q(z|x) \leq e^\epsilon Q(z|x') \quad \forall x, x', z . \quad (24)$$

For such locally private channels, standard information bounds (e.g., [20]) imply that there exists a constant $\zeta > 0$ (in nats) such that

$$I(X; G_W(X)) \leq \zeta \epsilon^2 . \quad (25)$$

Therefore, ϵ -LDP directly limits the gating information rate $R_g = I(X; G_W(X))$ and hence constrains the achievable rate-distortion performance through $D(R_g)$. In particular, if $R_g \leq \zeta \epsilon^2$, then by Theorem 2 we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(\zeta \epsilon^2) + \delta_m + \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} . \quad (26)$$

Any further reduction of $I(S; W)$ due to privacy mechanisms depends on the learning algorithm and is not asserted here.

Remark 3 (Capacity-limited MoE gating). *Suppose that the gating decisions $G_W(X)$ are conveyed over a physical communication link with per-sample Shannon capacity C nats, so that the achieved gating rate*

$$R_g \triangleq I(X; G_W(X)) \leq C .$$

Since $D(\cdot)$ is non-increasing, $R_g \leq C$ implies

$$D(R_g) \geq D(C) .$$

Therefore, Theorem 2 holds as stated with the achieved rate R_g :

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \leq D(R_g) + \delta_m + \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} , \quad R_g \leq C . \quad (27)$$

Moreover, under a near-saturation design in which $I(X; G_W(X)) \approx C$ (and (14) holds at rate of C), we have $D(R_g) \approx D(C)$, so the bound effectively specializes to

$$\mathbb{E}[R(W)] \lesssim D(C) + \delta_m + \sqrt{\frac{2}{m} I(S; W)} . \quad (28)$$

V. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

We next illustrate the applicability of Theorems 1 and 2 on two synthetic experiments. In the first experiment (Fig. 2), we consider a binary classification task generated by a true MoE model with real-valued Gaussian features. The true model has $d = 3$ input dimensions and 10 experts. A bank of 30 candidate MoE models is drawn i.i.d. from the same prior distribution. For each dataset of size $m = 5$, we compute the empirical 0–1 risk of every candidate model and use an α -mixture learning algorithm: with probability $1 - \alpha$ the learner samples a model uniformly at random, and with probability α it selects the empirical-risk minimizer. By sweeping α from 0 to 1, we obtain a family of learning algorithms with increasing dependence on the sample and hence increasing mutual information $I(S; W)$, estimated via $I(S; W) = H(W) - H(W|S)$ from the posterior $q(W|S)$. For each α we estimate the generalization gap $|\mathbb{E}[R(W)] - R_S(W)|$ by averaging over 100 datasets and a separate test set of size 1000.

Fig. 2 plots the empirical generalization gap as a function of the information term $\sqrt{2I(S; W)/m}$, together with the theoretical line $y = \sqrt{2I(S; W)/m}$. The points form an increasing curve that stays strictly below the diagonal, showing

Fig. 2: MoE simulation for Theorem 1. The empirical generalization gap $|\mathbb{E}[R] - R_S|$ increases with the information term $\sqrt{2I(S;W)/m}$ and remains below the theoretical upper bound, illustrating the info-generalization trade-off at the algorithm level.

that the mutual-information bound of Theorem 1 is respected and captures the growth of the generalization gap as the learner becomes more data-dependent.

In the second experiment (Fig. 3), we use a binary symmetric channel (BSC) setting that makes the rate-distortion structure explicit. We let $X \sim \text{Bernoulli}(1/2)$ and $Y = X \oplus Z$, where $Z \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p_{\text{true}})$ models noise. A finite candidate set $\{p_r\}$ of crossover probabilities is fixed, and for each dataset of size $m = 200$, we compute the log-likelihood of the observed sample under every candidate $\text{BSC}(p_r)$, form a tempered posterior over indices, and sample a single channel index W . The resulting model has crossover probability p_W , so its population risk is $R(W) = p_W$, and its gating rate is $R_g = I(X; G_W(X)) = \ln 2 - h(p_W)$ in nats, where $h(\cdot)$ denotes the binary entropy function (in nats). This toy channel can be viewed as a one-bit gating scenario, where the crossover probability p_W measures how accurately the gate routes X to the appropriate expert, and the rate $R_g = \ln 2 - h(p_W)$ represents the effective communication rate of this binary gating path. For each p_{true} in a grid, we run 400 Monte Carlo datasets, estimate $I(S; W)$ via entropies of the posterior, and evaluate the bound from Theorem 2 as

$$D(R_g) + \sqrt{(2/m)I(S;W)}, \quad (29)$$

where $D(R_g)$ is the BSC rate-distortion function in nats⁴.

Fig. 3 shows the analytical rate-distortion curve $D(R_g)$, the empirical mean population risks $\mathbb{E}[R(W)]$ obtained from the simulation, and the corresponding upper-bound values of Theorem 2. The empirical risks track $D(R_g)$ closely across a wide range of gating rates, while all simulated points lie comfortably below the theoretical curve in (29), thus illustrating the predicted rate-distortion-generalization trade-off.

VI. CONCLUSION

This letter established an explicit information-theoretic connection between the communication rate of the gating mechanism and the generalization performance of Mixture-of-Experts models. By casting the gate as a finite-capacity

⁴Note that, in this BSC setting, $D(R_g)$ is available in closed form and the rate term is evaluated analytically, so δ_m is negligible in the plotted bound.

Fig. 3: BSC rate-distortion-generalization experiment for Theorem 2. The empirical mean population risk $\mathbb{E}[R(W)]$ (dots) closely follows the rate-distortion curve $D(R_g)$, while the bound in (29) (triangles) remains safely above, confirming the theoretical trade-off between gating rate and prediction accuracy.

stochastic channel, we derived mutual-information and rate-distortion-generalization bounds in which the gating rate $I(X; G_W(X))$ appears as an operational capacity measure shaping both expressivity and statistical robustness.

From a practical standpoint, the analysis applies directly to communication-constrained learning scenarios such as federated MoE, edge or split inference, coded computing, and distributed aerospace systems, where expert routing must operate under strict bandwidth or reliability constraints [6], [7], [21]. In all such settings, the gating rate $I(X; G_W(X))$ functions as an operational communication rate (which in practice is upper-bounded by the available link capacity) that jointly governs statistical efficiency and model expressivity; in aerospace and autonomous platforms, it also quantifies the trade-off between communication rate, inference accuracy, and control responsiveness, extending classical data-rate theorems [9], [10] to modern learned decision systems. Future work includes extending these results to deeper and hierarchical MoE architectures, developing training procedures that explicitly regularize $I(X; G_W(X))$, and validating the theory on large-scale, bandwidth-limited deployments.

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